

Local Government in Switzerland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Switzerland: An Introduction

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The Swiss federal system is characterized by a strong orientation towards power sharing, concordance and compromise. Participation is seen as a means of integrating a diversity of views in decision-making, thus contributing to making state authorities at all levels accountable and responsive to its citizens, improving the quality of decisions taken and mitigating possible resistance, deepening legitimacy and credibility of State authorities, and managing conflicts and tensions between various groups.

To make participation effective, people need political space as well as access to information. The freedom of expression and information is guaranteed by the Swiss constitution (Article 16 of the Constitution). While citizens use various channels to inform and express their opinions, the media is a key contributor in forming an open public debate and serves as an important platform for information sharing and ensuring transparency (Article 17 of the Constitution). The Federal Act on Freedom of Information in the Administration seeks to promote transparency with regard to the mandate, organization and activities of the administration and grants the public access to official documents and information (Article 1 Freedom of Information Act). On cantonal and municipal levels there are similar laws and regulations.

The right to participation in political decision-making is a key feature of the Swiss federal system at all levels. The Swiss Constitution guarantees political rights including the 'freedom of the citizen to form an opinion and to give genuine expression to his or her will' for all levels (Article 34(2) of the Constitution, Article 136 of the Constitution). The exercise of political rights is regulated at federal level for federal matters only (Article 39(1) of the Constitution) while the cantons regulate their exercise at cantonal and municipal level. In the framework of cantonal law, municipalities enjoy 'autonomy' (Article 50 of the Constitution) which in principle includes the way how political processes in the municipalities are organized. In the 26 cantons laws and regulations differ in terms of space left to municipalities to design their own participatory approaches. Formal participation rights are usually reserved for Swiss citizens who are resident in the community at stake (political domicile) (Article 39(2) of the Constitution).

In the Swiss semi-direct democracy, the elected (representative) parliaments and (cantonal and local) governments are coupled with elements of direct democracy. The main instruments of popular participation include the following:

The popular initiative is a powerful tool for citizens, political parties and interest groups to influence the political agenda: At the federal level a constitutional amendment can be demanded with the signature of 100,000 Swiss citizens (see Articles 138ff of the Constitution). When an initiative is disposed, it is discussed by the government and the parliament. They take formal positions on the initiative, which may involve an alternative proposition. Initiatives and

counter-proposals must then be submitted to the popular vote. At cantonal and local level, the popular initiative can be used to propose laws and acts as well. The process that leads to popular votes varies among the cantons and municipalities.

Mandatory and optional referenda: At federal level, parliamentary decisions on amending the Federal Constitution, accessing organizations for collective security or supranational communities, and extra-constitutional emergency federal acts must be put to the popular vote (mandatory referendum, Article 140 of the Constitution). With the signature of 50,000 citizens or by the request of 8 (out of 26) cantons, new federal legislation or amendments to legislation can be called for a referendum (Article 141 of the Constitution). At cantonal level, the referenda systems are diverse and often include important administrative acts (such as important decisions on financial expenses, budgets, etc.). At municipal level, what is put to vote, depends on the municipal statute decided by the municipality. The instrument of referendum broadly impacts on the way how political decisions are taken: Swiss authorities at all levels often tend to seek broad majorities for their decisions to avoid a vote.

In smaller rural municipalities (particularly in the German speaking area) main decisions are often taken in citizen's assemblies where all residents of the respective municipality who are Swiss citizens can participate. In conformity with the cantonal law and municipal statutes, the assembly takes legislative, administrative and financial decisions that are mostly submitted by the municipal executive. In other (bigger and urban) municipalities, a municipal parliament is representing the citizens, mostly complemented with a referendum system allowing citizens for direct impact.

Various types of formal and informal consultation processes ensure that the different views of stakeholders are taken to account from the beginning and integrated into political processes – often to mitigate the risk of a referendum that may skip the final decision in the end. At federal level, the government is obliged to invite the cantons, the political parties and interested groups to 'express their views when preparing important legislation or other projects of substantial impact as well as in relation to significant international treaties' (Article 47 of the Constitution). Parallel provisions can be found in the cantonal constitutions. Some federal and cantonal laws and regulations foresee specific consultation procedures in particular domains that affect cantonal and/or municipal decision-making in particular. Municipal consultations refer to many policy fields such as spatial planning, local development strategies, infrastructure projects, environment and energy issues, tourism, traffic issues, or municipal amalgamation processes. Such consultations can take many forms (e.g. hearings, exchange platforms, round tables, information campaigns, etc.). They may target the broad public or specific groups that are perceived by the authorities as potential supporters or spoilers. Some municipalities have established specific consultation processes that involve neighborhood residents in decision-making when they are particularly affected by the matter at stake. Individual processes are foreseen in many municipalities to incorporate specific stakeholder groups on particular topics (Children and youth, parents, elderly people, non-Swiss residents).

The right to petition is guaranteed by the Swiss Constitution as well as established at cantonal and municipal level.

In general, the new media have changed the ways how people express their opinion, communicate among interest groups and with the authorities. New forms and collaborative methods of participation have developed in recent years that complement more traditional forms of participation, particularly at municipal level. Recent research suggests that the executive is increasingly perceiving participation as a means of improving governability in complex and politically fragmented situations. The often relatively low numbers of citizens that are participating also suggest that these new forms are not broadening but deepening participation by targeting certain citizens and groups that are already engaged in political processes.

All these formal instruments invite stakeholders and citizens to participate but in reality, they may not be accessible for marginalized groups, and many of them formally exclude non-citizens. Individual activists and specific interest groups often invent their own spaces and forms to influence the political agenda and the decision-making processes at all levels (e.g. public manifestations of different kinds, protests and 'strikes', media campaigns, citizens' gatherings). In many cases, these 'invented' forms are in one way or another related to more formal instruments such as initiatives and referenda.

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